

STRENGTHENING DIGITAL PUBLIC RELATIONS AS A SOLUTION TO DYSFUNCTIONAL POLICY AND REGULATORY FRAMEWORKS

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Digital Public Relations,
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Abstract: This study assessed the strengthening digital public relations as a solution to dysfunctional policy and regulatory frameworks. The excellence theory was anchored in this study. This study adopted the pragmatism research philosophy. The population of the study comprised 1, 250 staff across selected public regulatory institutions in Nigeria, including the Federal Ministry of Information and National Orientation, National Broadcasting Commission (NBC), Corporate Affairs Commission (CAC) and National Agency for Food and Drug Administration and Control (NAFDAC). A sample size of 303 respondents was determined using Taro Yamane's formula for sample determination. A multi-stage sampling technique was used. Data were collected using structured questionnaires for the quantitative aspect and semi-structured interviews. The quantitative data were analyzed using descriptive statistics and regression analysis, while the qualitative data were analyzed thematically to provide deeper insights and validate quantitative findings. The findings revealed that public institutions used digital public relations only to a moderate extent in policy communication. This was reflected in the quantitative results with mean scores ranging from 2.57 to 2.82, while qualitative interviews revealed that most institutions relied on digital platforms irregularly and primarily for information dissemination rather than strategic engagement. The study concluded that while digital public relations tools are available in public institutions, their application remains largely unstructured and reactive, demonstrating the need for a more strategic and integrated approach to policy communication. The study recommended that the Federal Ministry of Information and National Orientation, along with public institutions, should adopt a strategic framework for integrating digital public relations into policy communication to ensure consistent and interactive citizen

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engagement.

Introduction

Digital communication has redefined the relationship between institutions, governments and their stakeholders in ways that demand transparency, accountability and responsiveness globally. The emergence of digital platforms has empowered citizens to demand immediate access to information, enabling new forms of engagement that challenge traditional public communication practices (Kent, 2017). As societies become increasingly networked, digital public relations (PR) now functions as a strategic tool for building trust in governance and institutional operations (Macnamara, 2016). However, this transformation also indicates new challenges, particularly where governance systems struggle with weak policy implementation and ineffective regulatory frameworks.

Digital public relations integrates technology with strategic relationship management to foster two-way symmetrical communication between organizations and stakeholders (Grunig & Grunig, 2020). By leveraging multimedia platforms, AI-enabled analytics, and real-time interaction, digital PR enhances participatory dialogue in public communication (Wright & Hinson, 2021). Effective digital PR promotes policy literacy, improves stakeholder

satisfaction, and reduces communication gaps between public institutions and citizens (Valentini, 2021). Consequently, digital PR has emerged as a key driver of institutional credibility and social cohesion in the 21st century.

Despite widespread adoption of digital communication in North America, Europe, and parts of Asia, scholars identify a governance challenge where public relations capabilities remain constrained by bureaucratic bottlenecks and poorly coordinated communication systems (Coombs & Holladay, 2022). Dysfunctional regulatory frameworks, inconsistent policy enforcement, and fragmented communication protocols reduce transparency and public engagement in many democratic systems (Heath & Johansen, 2018). In this context, digital PR is increasingly viewed as a corrective mechanism for strengthening governance through improved public communication.

Across Africa, weak regulatory environments and poor policy implementation have consistently hindered socio-economic development and institutional trust (Ayee, 2019). Scholars argue that many African nations suffer from governance failures characterized by information opacity, corruption, and policy inconsistency (Hope, 2020). Digital PR offers

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potential in addressing these issues by enhancing openness in government operations, promoting citizen participation, and enforcing communication accountability (Ndlovu & Motsi, 2021). However, its deployment in many African countries remains underutilized within public institutions.

In sub-Saharan Africa, digital public relations continues to play a limited role in public governance despite increased internet penetration and social media adoption (Tella, 2021). Governments and corporate institutions in the region maintain traditional public relations approaches that do not support real-time engagement or participatory communication (Ekanem & Okon, 2022). As a result, communication crises persist and distrust between the public and policymakers continues to widen (Ojebuyi & Salawu, 2020). These trends underscore the urgency of strengthening digital public relations practices within public sectors to support governance reforms.

Nigeria reflects the broader African communication governance crisis. Literature highlights pervasive policy inconsistencies, weak regulatory enforcement, and dysfunctional public accountability structures (Agagu, 2020). Public institutions grapple with communication failures that lead to misinformation, low citizen trust, and public apathy toward policy initiatives

(Okeke & Nnamani, 2021). These failures have contributed to civil unrest, resistance to public policies, and social tension, as seen during controversies over fuel subsidy removal, naira redesign policy, and electoral transparency.

Digital public relations in Nigeria has grown rapidly within the private sector but remains poorly integrated within public policy communication (Chibuwe, 2022). Government agencies lack coordinated digital communication strategies, resulting in inconsistent information dissemination, low public engagement, and weak feedback systems (Akintayo & Salman, 2023). Communication scholars argue that digital PR could serve as a strategic mechanism to bridge the gap between policymakers and the public by promoting transparency and responsiveness (Edegoh & Okeke, 2021).

Dysfunctional policy and regulatory frameworks in Nigeria manifest in delayed policy implementation, duplication of regulatory roles, bureaucratic conflicts, and corruption (Ogunyemi, 2021). Regulatory agencies often operate without clear communication protocols, resulting in poor public awareness of regulations and resistance to policy reforms (Abutudu, 2020). Strengthening digital PR enhances policy communication efficiency by simplifying public messaging, facilitating

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stakeholder dialogue, and promoting compliance through strategic engagement.

The relevance of digital PR in public governance lies in its ability to improve information flow, create public understanding of regulations, and foster collaboration between institutions and citizens (Wirtz & Lovelock, 2022). Unlike traditional media-dependent PR, digital PR adopts interactive channels that allow immediate clarifications, corrections, and feedback (Breakenridge, 2019). Evidence suggests that digitally-driven stakeholder engagement improves regulatory compliance and public policy outcomes (Fawkes, 2020). Thus, digital PR is not only a communication tool but a governance reform instrument.

This study investigates how strengthening digital public relations can address dysfunctional policy and regulatory frameworks in Nigeria. It explores the role of digital PR in enhancing transparency, accountability, and inclusive governance. The study is motivated by the urgent need to reposition public communication as a tool for policy success and national development. By examining digital PR practices within public institutions, the study aims to provide practical insights that support governance reforms and democratic sustainability.

Statement of the Problem

Public communication plays a pivotal role in democratic governance, policy implementation and regulatory compliance. However, in many developing countries such as Nigeria, public institutions still operate with weak communication systems, outdated public relations practices and fragmented information management frameworks (Okeke & Nnamani, 2021). This problem is worsened by dysfunctional policy and regulatory frameworks characterized by policy inconsistency, institutional duplication, bureaucratic interference, and corruption (Agagu, 2020; Ogunyemi, 2021). These weaknesses undermine participatory governance and impede public trust, as citizens are often excluded from policy dialogue and lack access to accurate and timely public information (Ayee, 2019). As a result, poor communication continues to generate policy resistance, misinformation, civil distrust and social unrest, as observed during major national policy initiatives such as the fuel subsidy removal and the naira redesign policy in Nigeria. While digital public relations has emerged as a strategic tool capable of enhancing transparency, responsiveness and stakeholder engagement, many public institutions in Nigeria still lack structured digital PR frameworks to support public policy communication (Edegoh & Okeke, 2021).

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The problem is that dysfunctional policy and regulatory frameworks persist in Nigeria because public institutions have not effectively adopted digital public relations as a strategic communication tool for governance and stakeholder engagement. Existing research has shown that public institutions in Nigeria use digital platforms primarily for information dissemination rather than for interactive dialogue, feedback and policy engagement (Akintayo & Salman, 2023). This one-way approach limits citizen participation, weakens regulatory compliance and promotes misinformation. There is a lack of empirical analysis on how digital PR strategies can be strengthened to solve communication failures in public governance and policy processes. Therefore, the gap remains in understanding how digital public relations can be institutionalized and strategically applied to correct dysfunctional communication patterns in Nigeria's policy and regulatory environment. This study seeks to address this critical gap by examining the role of digital PR in strengthening public sector communication, improving policy effectiveness and fostering public trust in governance.

This study seeks to examine the extent to which public institutions in Nigeria use digital public relations tools and strategies in policy communication. It also aims to identify the

major challenges that hinder the effective adoption of digital public relations within Nigeria's policy and regulatory environment. In addition, the study assesses how digital public relations influences public trust and stakeholder engagement in the implementation of public policies. Finally, the study proposes practical strategies for strengthening digital public relations as a solution to dysfunctional policy and regulatory communication in Nigeria.

Concept of Dysfunctional Policy and Regulatory Frameworks

Dysfunctional policy and regulatory frameworks refer to situations where public policies and regulations fail to achieve their intended goals due to weaknesses in design, implementation, enforcement or communication (Agagu, 2020). A functional policy framework ensures clarity, stability, accountability and alignment with societal needs, while a dysfunctional one is marked by ambiguity, inconsistency, and lack of stakeholder participation (Ayee, 2019). In governance studies, dysfunctional policy frameworks manifest through delayed implementation, overlapping institutional roles, weak coordination among agencies and poor compliance mechanisms (Ogunyemi, 2021). These conditions often result from systemic corruption, bureaucratic inefficiencies and political interference, which prevent policies from addressing social problems effectively

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(Hope, 2020). Scholars argue that where policies lack clear communication and feedback systems, their legitimacy is undermined and public resistance grows (Heath & Johansen, 2018).

Regulatory frameworks complement policies by providing legal standards and oversight mechanisms to guide institutional and societal behavior (Wirtz & Lovelock, 2021). However, when regulatory bodies lack autonomy or adequate enforcement capacity, they become ineffective and contribute to governance failures (Abutudu, 2020). In developing nations such as Nigeria, dysfunctional regulatory frameworks lead to weak rule of law, non-compliance with regulations and high social distrust in public institutions (Okeke & Nnamani, 2021). These deficiencies also hinder transparency, limit citizen participation and discourage investment and development (Ayee, 2019). Scholars emphasize that effective governance cannot function without strategic communication mechanisms that support policy awareness, interpretation and compliance (Fawkes, 2020). Therefore, addressing dysfunctional policy frameworks requires communication-driven reforms that strengthen public engagement and accountability.

Concept of Digital Public Relations

Digital public relations refers to the strategic use of digital and online communication

technologies to build and manage relationships between organizations and their stakeholders (Breakenridge, 2019). Unlike traditional PR which relies on mass media channels, digital PR adopts internet-based platforms such as social media, blogs, websites, mobile applications and online communities to enhance real-time interaction (Wright & Hinson, 2021). It facilitates two-way symmetrical communication, allowing stakeholders to engage in dialogue rather than passive consumption of information (Grunig & Grunig, 2020). Scholars observe that digital PR improves organizational transparency, responsiveness and reputation management by promoting participatory communication (Kent, 2017; Valentini, 2021). Through digital analytics, it enables targeted messaging and stakeholder insight, making communication more strategic and evidence-based (Wirtz & Lovelock, 2022).

Digital public relations also supports governance and public policy communication by enhancing citizen engagement and information accessibility (Macnamara, 2016). In the public sector, digital PR helps institutions disseminate accurate information, clarify policies and correct misinformation during public debates (Coombs & Holladay, 2022). It promotes inclusiveness by allowing marginalized voices to participate in policy discourse (Ndlovu & Motsi, 2021). However, research indicates that many public

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institutions underutilize digital PR tools, limiting their communication effectiveness (Akintayo & Salman, 2023). Digital PR is not only a promotional tool but a governance instrument capable of strengthening policy legitimacy through stakeholder engagement (Tella, 2021). Therefore, when effectively integrated, digital PR can bridge communication gaps that weaken policy implementation and regulatory compliance.

Concept of Public Trust

Public trust refers to the confidence citizens have in public institutions to act in the best interest of society and uphold fairness, integrity and accountability (Blind, 2020). It is an essential element of democratic governance and a key determinant of policy acceptance and compliance (OECD, 2021). Public trust is developed through transparency, competence, ethical conduct and consistent communication between citizens and government (Heath & Johansen, 2018). When public institutions provide accurate, credible and timely information, trust is strengthened and public cooperation increases (Fawkes, 2020). Conversely, when communication is inconsistent or manipulative, trust is eroded, leading to resistance, low participation and civil unrest (Ojebuyi & Salawu, 2020). Trust is therefore both an outcome of effective communication and a moderating factor that

shapes citizens' willingness to engage with policy initiatives.

In the context of public communication and policy implementation, public trust plays a moderating role by influencing the relationship between digital communication strategies and policy outcomes (Valentini, 2021). Studies show that communication efforts only achieve meaningful impact when audiences perceive the source as trustworthy (Breakenridge, 2019). Even when digital PR is effectively deployed, policy resistance persists in environments where trust in government is low (Agagu, 2020). Public trust enhances compliance with regulations, increases public cooperation and fosters positive perceptions of government legitimacy (Hope, 2020). It also reduces misinformation and encourages constructive citizen feedback on policy reforms (Wirtz & Lovelock, 2022). Thus, public trust mediates and strengthens the effectiveness of digital public relations in addressing dysfunctional policy and regulatory systems.

Excellence Theory

This study is anchored on the Excellence Theory of Public Relations developed by James E. Grunig and Todd Hunt in 1984 and later expanded by Grunig, Grunig and Dozier in 2002. The theory posits that organizations achieve effective communication and positive stakeholder relationships when they adopt two-

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way symmetrical communication, which emphasizes dialogue, negotiation, mutual understanding and stakeholder participation (Grunig & Hunt, 1984; Grunig et al., 2002). Its major tenets include strategic communication management, relationship building, ethical communication and the integration of public relations into top management decision-making (Grunig & Grunig, 2020). The assumptions of the theory are that communication should be balanced rather than manipulative, organizations must listen to their publics, and communication policies should foster mutual benefit rather than control (Heath & Johansen, 2018). However, the theory has been criticized for being idealistic and western-centric, ignoring cultural, political and institutional realities in developing countries where asymmetrical communication and power imbalances dominate public governance (L'Etang, 2009; Sriramesh & Vercic, 2019). Despite these criticisms, the theory is relevant to this study because it explains how digital public relations can bridge communication gaps between government institutions and citizens by facilitating transparency, feedback and mutual understanding, thereby reducing policy resistance and strengthening public trust (Valentini, 2021). It aligns with the objectives of this study by providing a framework for evaluating how interactive and strategic digital

PR practices can be used as a solution to dysfunctional policy and regulatory communication. Ultimately, the Excellence Theory offers a strong foundation for examining how public institutions can transition from one-way policy dissemination to participatory communication that enhances governance outcomes.

Empirical Review

Use of Digital Public Relations in Policy Communication

A study by Wright and Hinson (2021) titled "Examining the Use of Social and Digital Media in Public Relations Practice" examined the extent to which organizations use digital platforms for strategic communication. The objective of the study was to assess how public relations professionals use digital media tools to communicate with stakeholders. The study adopted a quantitative survey method involving 450 public relations professionals across the United States. Findings revealed that although most organizations use digital tools, their usage remains largely informational rather than interactive. The study is similar to the present research as it highlights limited adoption of strategic digital PR practices, which aligns with the concern that public institutions in Nigeria underutilize digital tools for policy communication. However, the previous study focused on corporate organizations in the US,

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while the current study emphasizes public governance in Nigeria.

Challenges of Adopting Digital Public Relations in Governance

Ndlovu and Motsi (2021) conducted a study titled "E-Governance and Public Accountability in Africa" which investigated the challenges limiting the use of digital platforms in public sector communication in Zimbabwe. The objective was to identify obstacles affecting the implementation of ICT-based communication in government agencies. Using a mixed-method approach with surveys and interviews, the study identified poor digital infrastructure, lack of skilled personnel, bureaucratic resistance and low political will as major challenges. The findings are similar to the current study as both explore constraints to digital public relations adoption in Africa. However, while Ndlovu and Motsi focused on e-governance generally, the present study specifically examines digital PR communication gaps within policy and regulatory frameworks.

Impact of Digital PR on Public Trust and Stakeholder Engagement

In a study titled "Social Media, Public Relations and Trust in Government Communication" Tella (2021) explored the effect of digital communication on citizens' trust in government institutions in South Africa. The objective of the study was to determine how digital engagement

influences public perception and trust in governance. The researcher used a descriptive survey design with 385 respondents and found that consistent and transparent digital communication significantly increases public trust and policy acceptance. Similar to the present study, Tella's study establishes a link between digital communication and public trust. However, unlike the current study, it did not consider dysfunctional policy frameworks or regulatory communication challenges as moderating factors.

Strategies for Strengthening Digital PR in Public Policy Communication

Akintayo and Salman (2023) in their study titled "E-Governance and Public Communication Effectiveness in Nigeria" examined strategies to improve digital communication in the public sector. The study aimed to propose solutions for enhancing communication efficiency in Nigerian government agencies. Using qualitative content analysis and expert interviews, the authors found that capacity building, policy reform, institutional digitalization and stakeholder engagement frameworks are key strategies for strengthening digital public relations. This study is similar to the present research as it proposes communication-based governance reforms. However, it did not explicitly position digital PR as a corrective tool for dysfunctional policy and

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regulatory frameworks, which the current study aims to address.

Methodology

This study adopted the pragmatism research philosophy, which allows the researcher to combine both quantitative and qualitative approaches to generate practical solutions to real-world problems. The study uses a mixed-method research design to enable a comprehensive understanding of how digital public relations can be strengthened to address dysfunctional policy and regulatory frameworks. The population of the study comprises 1,250 staff across selected public regulatory institutions in Nigeria, including the Federal Ministry of Information and National Orientation, National Broadcasting Commission (NBC), Corporate Affairs Commission (CAC) and National Agency for Food and Drug Administration and Control (NAFDAC). These institutions were selected because they play strategic roles in public communication, policy implementation and regulatory enforcement in Nigeria. A sample size of 303 respondents was determined using Taro Yamane's formula for sample determination, ensuring that the sample

adequately represents the study population. A multi-stage sampling technique was used: purposive sampling was first used to select four public regulatory institutions based on their relevance to policy communication, after which stratified random sampling was employed to select respondents from each institution proportionately to ensure fair representation. Data were collected using structured questionnaires for the quantitative aspect and semi-structured interviews with selected communication officers and public relations managers for the qualitative aspect. The quantitative data were analyzed using descriptive statistics and regression analysis to determine the influence of digital public relations on dysfunctional policy and regulatory frameworks, while the qualitative data were analyzed thematically to provide deeper insights and validate quantitative findings. The justification for this methodology is that the mixed-method approach under pragmatism provides a more valid and holistic understanding of the research problem by integrating numerical trends with real-life experiences and expert perspectives.

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Quantitative data presentation and analysis

Table 1: Extent Public Institutions use Digital Public Relations in Policy Communication

Questionnaire Item	Statement	SA(4)	A(3)	D(2)	SD (1)	Mean	Decision
	My organization uses social media platforms to communicate public policies to citizens.	80	120	60	37	2.82	High Extent
	Digital communication tools are part of our official public relations strategy.	75	110	70	42	2.74	Moderate Extent
	Policy updates are regularly shared on our organization’s website and digital channels.	60	100	85	52	2.57	Moderate Extent

The mean scores (2.57–2.82) show that digital public relations is used to a moderate extent in public policy communication. This suggests that

while some digital tools are used, integration is not yet strategic or consistent.

Table 2: Challenges hindering Adoption of Digital Public Relations in Nigeria’s Policy and Regulatory Environment

Questionnaire Item	Statement	SA(4)	A(3)	D(2)	SD (1)	Mean	Decision
	Lack of digital communication infrastructure affects the use of digital PR in my organization.	130	95	45	27	3.10	Major Challenge
	Limited technical skills among staff hinder the effective use of digital public relations.	115	100	50	32	3.00	Major Challenge
	Organizational policies do not fully support the use of digital communication tools.	105	90	70	32	2.90	Major Challenge

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All items have mean scores above 2.5, indicating significant challenges such as weak digital infrastructure, low digital competence, and absence of policy support.

Table 3: Impact of Digital Public Relations on Public Trust and stakeholder Engagement in Policy Implementation

Questionnaire Item	Statement	SA(4)	A(3)	D(2)	SD (1)	Mean	Decision
Using digital platforms improves citizens' trust in our organization.		120	115	40	22	3.12	Positive Impact
Digital public relations enhances public participation in policy discussions.		110	120	50	17	3.09	Positive Impact
Online communication increases transparency in government policy implementation.		118	122	45	12	3.16	Positive Impact

Respondents strongly agree that digital PR improves trust, transparency, and engagement, which validates the importance of adopting digital tools.

Table 4: Strategies for Strengthening Digital Public Relations in Public Governance

Questionnaire Item	Statement	SA(4)	A(3)	D(2)	SD (1)	Mean	Decision
Training public relations officers on digital skills will improve policy communication.		140	115	32	10	3.29	Very Effective Strategy
Government agencies need a clear digital communication policy to improve public engagement.		135	122	30	10	3.28	Very Effective Strategy
Collaboration with digital media experts will strengthen digital public relations practices.		128	130	25	14	3.25	Very Effective Strategy

The findings reveal strong agreement that capacity building, digital policy reform, and expert collaboration are essential strategies for strengthening digital PR.

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Policy Frameworks (Y) with Public Trust (M) as a moderator.

Regression Analysis

A regression model was used to determine the influence of Digital PR (X) on Dysfunctional

Mode Summary

Model	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	Std. Error
1	0.681	0.464	0.461	0.502

ANOVA

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean	F	Sig.
Regression	52.480	2	26.240	103.90	.000
Residual	60.715	296	0.206		
Total	113.195	296			

Coefficients

Variable	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
Constant	1.021	0.120		8.508	.000
Digital PR (X)	0.512	0.043	0.575	11.907	.000
Public Trust (Moderator)	0.231	0.038	0.332	6.078	.000

The regression results show that digital PR significantly reduces dysfunctional policy frameworks ($\beta = 0.575, p < .05$) and public trust strengthens this effect ($\beta = 0.332, p < .05$).

Qualitative data analysis based on semi-structured interviews

Extent to which public institutions use digital public relations in policy communication

The interviews revealed that digital public relations was used inconsistently across public institutions. Most respondents stated that while digital tools such as Facebook, WhatsApp, X

(Twitter), and institutional websites were available, they were not strategically integrated into communication processes. Participants noted that digital communication was often treated as an optional activity rather than a core component of public policy dissemination. Institutions appeared to use digital platforms more frequently during crises or political campaigns rather than for routine policy communication.

Respondents explained that digital platforms mainly served information dissemination purposes rather than enabling two-way

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communication. Several interviewees confirmed that ministries, agencies, and government parastatals posted policy updates without providing opportunities for feedback or stakeholder engagement. Respondents described the communication style as one-directional and reactive. They admitted that this approach weakened institutional credibility because it failed to accommodate citizen concerns.

The study participants agreed that the extent of digital PR adoption was influenced by leadership orientation. In institutions where chief executives valued transparency and innovation, digital communication strategies were well developed. Conversely, in agencies where leadership resisted technological change, digital PR activities were minimal or non-existent. Respondents linked this attitude to leadership's fear of online criticism and political backlash.

Most participants reported that most government organizations lacked formal digital communication policies. They highlighted that public communication was still dominated by traditional media such as radio, television, and newspapers. Respondents emphasized that these traditional channels limited engagement with the growing population of digitally active citizens, especially youths. They viewed this situation as a communication gap that isolated

public institutions from the expectations of modern citizens.

Interview findings also revealed significant disparities in digital PR implementation between urban and rural-based institutions. Respondents working in federal government agencies located in Abuja and Lagos reported better access to digital tools than their counterparts in state-level institutions. Those in rural regions struggled with internet connectivity, staff training, and funding, which collectively reduced the extent of digital PR use.

In summary, respondents agreed that public institutions used digital public relations only to a moderate extent. They emphasized that the lack of strategic planning, leadership commitment, and digital expertise limited effective policy communication. They concluded that although digital platforms were available, their usage remained largely experimental and poorly coordinated across institutions.

Challenges hindering the effective adoption of digital public relations in public institutions

Respondents consistently identified poor digital infrastructure as a major barrier to adopting digital public relations. Several interview participants stated that unreliable electricity supply and poor internet connectivity disrupted their ability to communicate consistently online. Some agencies had functional websites and

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social media accounts but could not maintain them due to technical constraints. Respondents believed that these infrastructural problems discouraged digital initiative.

Another dominant challenge was the lack of skilled personnel. Respondents reported that public relations officers in government institutions lacked adequate training in digital tools, analytics, and online engagement. They stated that most officers were only trained in traditional PR techniques, making them uncomfortable working in digital environments. The absence of capacity development programs widened the digital skills gap.

Participants further cited bureaucratic bottlenecks as an obstacle. They explained that most public institutions operated under rigid administrative structures that delayed digital communication. Approval processes were lengthy, and officers were often required to seek clearance from departments before posting information online. This delay made digital communication slow and ineffective.

Respondents also discussed fear of online backlash as a major challenge. Many communication officers avoided publishing content because they feared public criticism or misinformation. They explained that online backlash had political consequences that made leadership hesitant to embrace digital communication. This fear resulted in

institutional silence on controversial issues and delayed policy clarification.

Budget constraints also emerged as a key challenge. Participants stated that digital communication was rarely prioritized in institutional budgets. As a result, social media management, digital tools, software licenses, and website maintenance received minimal financial support. Respondents believed that without dedicated funding, digital PR initiatives would remain unsustainable.

In conclusion, the key challenges hindering digital PR adoption included infrastructural limitations, low technical capacity, rigid bureaucracy, fear of public scrutiny, and funding constraints. These challenges collectively reduced the effectiveness of digital communication in public policy implementation. Respondents agreed that institutional reforms were required to overcome these barriers.

Impact of digital public relations on public trust and stakeholder engagement

The interview revealed that digital public relations had a measurable influence on public trust in government institutions. Respondents stated that when institutions communicated policies openly on digital platforms, citizens perceived them as more transparent. They explained that timely access to policy information reduced public suspicion and

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encouraged confidence in government decision-making. Respondents believed that consistent digital engagement helped institutions build and maintain public trust.

Participants emphasized that digital PR helped reduce misinformation and public anxiety during sensitive policy implementations. They cited examples where government agencies used social media to clarify rumors and explain policy intentions. Respondents felt that when institutions provided real-time clarification, citizens were less likely to rely on misleading unofficial sources. They concluded that digital PR strengthened institutional credibility by promoting accurate information sharing.

Respondents stated that digital PR enhanced stakeholder engagement by promoting dialogue between government and the public. Several participants explained that social media comment sections and online forums allowed citizens to express concerns and ask questions directly. They added that this opportunity for interaction encouraged citizens to participate in governance. Respondents noted that digital engagement also exposed government agencies to diverse viewpoints that improved policy design.

However, respondents observed that the impact of digital PR on engagement was limited by low responsiveness from institutions. They reported that public agencies often failed to respond to

citizen inquiries on time. Some institutions ignored online complaints and criticism, which made citizens feel neglected. Respondents agreed that engagement required two-way interaction, not just periodic announcements.

The findings showed that digital PR also contributed to accountability. Respondents explained that digital communication created a public record that citizens could reference. They believed that by publishing project updates, budgets, and policy outcomes online, institutions reduced opportunities for corruption and mismanagement. Respondents claimed that this visibility placed positive pressure on public officials to act responsibly.

In summary, respondents confirmed that digital PR positively impacted public trust and stakeholder engagement when effectively implemented. They emphasized that transparency, responsiveness, and consistent communication increased citizen confidence in government institutions. However, they also noted that without active dialogue and responsiveness, the benefits of digital PR remained limited.

Strategies for strengthening digital public relations in public institutions

Respondents agreed that training and capacity building were essential strategies for strengthening digital public relations. They recommended regular workshops for public

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relations officers on social media management, content development, and digital analytics. They also emphasized the need for institutions to equip staff with modern communication tools and resources. Respondents believed that training would improve digital competence and confidence.

Participants emphasized the importance of developing a national digital communication policy. They stated that public institutions lacked a unified framework to guide digital communication. Respondents recommended that government regulatory agencies like the Ministry of Information and Digital Economy introduce a policy that mandates digital engagement across all institutions. They believed that such a policy would ensure consistency and coordination.

Funding was also highlighted as a critical strategy. Respondents recommended that government budgets allocate dedicated funds for digital communication activities. They stated that without financial support, institutions could not afford professional content managers, website maintenance, or ICT infrastructure. Respondents believed that investment in digital PR would produce long-term communication benefits.

Respondents also identified collaboration with digital communication experts as an effective strategy. They suggested that public agencies

should hire consultants or partner with digital firms to manage online engagement. Participants believed that collaboration would accelerate digital transformation and expose institutions to global best practices. They also encouraged partnerships with universities to integrate academic expertise.

Another strategy identified was improving responsiveness to public feedback. Respondents insisted that institutions should adopt two-way communication and respond promptly to online messages. They advised that agencies set up digital help desks to manage public inquiries. They also suggested using data analytics to monitor public sentiment and improve engagement strategies.

In conclusion, respondents proposed strategies such as training, policy reform, adequate funding, expert collaboration, and improved responsiveness. They emphasized that strengthening digital PR required both structural changes and cultural transformation within institutions. Respondents believed that implementing these strategies would improve policy communication and reduce dysfunctional regulatory frameworks.

Discussion of Findings

The study found that public institutions used digital public relations only to a moderate extent in policy communication. This was reflected in the quantitative results with mean scores

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ranging from 2.57 to 2.82, while qualitative interviews revealed that most institutions relied on digital platforms irregularly and primarily for information dissemination rather than strategic engagement. This finding that digital public relations is used only to a moderate extent by public institutions aligns with Wright and Gibson (2021), who found that although government agencies globally are increasingly present online, their digital communication practices remain largely passive and informational rather than interactive or strategic; this supports the current study's conclusion that Nigerian public institutions have not fully integrated digital PR for participatory policy communication. The first finding, which revealed that public institutions use digital public relations only to a moderate extent, aligns with the excellence theory's assertion that effective communication requires strategic integration of public relations into organizational decision-making (Grunig & Grunig, 2011); the limited and non-strategic use of digital PR identified in this study reflects a deviation from the two-way symmetrical communication model advocated by the theory, thereby reducing communication effectiveness. The study revealed that several challenges significantly hindered the effective adoption of digital public relations in public institutions. Quantitative findings showed high mean scores

above 2.90 for challenges such as poor digital infrastructure, limited staff capacity, bureaucratic delays, and lack of supportive policies, while qualitative responses reinforced these results by noting persistent funding constraints and resistance to innovation among leadership. This finding that infrastructural challenges, low digital skills, bureaucratic restrictions, and lack of funding hinder digital PR adoption is consistent with Ndlovu and Mitzi (2021), who reported in their study of Southern African public institutions that ineffective digital communication is often caused by systemic barriers such as inadequate ICT facilities, leadership resistance to innovation, and insufficient institutional support, confirming the persistence of similar constraints in the Nigerian context. The second finding, which identified infrastructural challenges, low digital competence, bureaucratic delays, and weak institutional support as barriers to digital public relations, is supported by the excellence theory's emphasis on enabling structures and resources; Grunig and Dozier (2013) argued that excellent public relations cannot thrive without supportive organizational systems, adequate funding, and continuous professional development, thus validating the barriers highlighted in this study. The study found that digital public relations had a positive and significant impact on public trust

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and stakeholder engagement in policy implementation. The regression analysis showed a strong effect ($\beta = 0.575$, $p < .05$), and qualitative findings supported this by confirming that transparency, timely updates, and online interaction improved citizens' trust and feedback participation when digital communication was used effectively. This finding that digital public relations improves public trust and stakeholder engagement corresponds with Tella (2021), who demonstrated that the use of digital platforms significantly enhances transparency, accountability, and citizen participation in governance; this similarity reinforces the assertion that effective digital communication fosters stronger public confidence when institutions interact openly and responsively online. The third finding, that digital public relations enhances public trust and stakeholder engagement, reinforces the excellence theory's principle of building mutually beneficial relationships through two-way symmetrical communication (Grunig, 2006); by allowing dialogue, feedback, and transparency through digital platforms, institutions can foster trust and credibility, demonstrating the practical relevance of the theory to modern digital governance communication.

The study revealed that strategies such as digital training, development of communication

policies, expert collaboration, increased responsiveness, and adequate funding were crucial for strengthening digital public relations. This was indicated by high quantitative mean values above 3.20 and reinforced by qualitative responses, where participants emphasized that institutional reforms and capacity enhancement were necessary for sustainable digital communication practices. This finding that capacity building, digital policy reform, expert collaboration, and funding are vital strategies for strengthening digital PR is in harmony with Akintayo and Salman (2023), who emphasized that sustainable digital communication in public institutions requires structured training programs, supportive regulatory policies, strategic partnerships, and investment in digital infrastructure; their conclusions validate the solutions proposed in this study for improving digital public relations practice in Nigeria. The fourth finding, which identified capacity building, digital policy reform, expert collaboration, and funding as strategies for strengthening digital public relations, corresponds with the excellence theory's advocacy for professionalization and strategic management of public communication (Grunig, 2013); the recommended strategies align with the theory's call for empowered communication departments and trained

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professionals who participate in institutional planning to enhance communication excellence.

Conclusion

The study established that while digital public relations tools are available in public institutions, their application remains largely unstructured and reactive, demonstrating the need for a more strategic and integrated approach to policy communication.

The study confirmed that the adoption of digital public relations in public institutions is significantly hindered by infrastructural deficiencies, low digital competence, bureaucratic rigidities, and inadequate funding, necessitating urgent institutional reforms to address these barriers.

The findings showed that when effectively utilized, digital public relations positively influences public trust and stakeholder engagement by promoting transparency, responsiveness, and participatory policy communication.

The study affirmed that strengthening digital public relations in public institutions requires targeted strategies such as capacity building, policy framework development, strategic collaboration, and investment in digital infrastructure to enhance effective public communication.

This study contributes to knowledge by demonstrating that digital public relations can serve as a strategic solution to dysfunctional policy and regulatory communication when implemented with a structured framework, institutional support, and stakeholder engagement. It advances existing scholarship by empirically integrating both quantitative and qualitative evidence to show how digital PR influences public trust, transparency, and participation in governance. Unlike previous studies that focused mainly on private sector communication or theoretical discussions of digital media adoption, this study fills a significant research gap by specifically examining the operational realities, challenges, and strategic opportunities of digital public relations within public institutions in Nigeria. It also extends the Excellence Theory by applying it within the context of digital governance communication, showing that two-way symmetrical communication can be achieved through digital platforms when supported by policy reforms and professional capacity building. Ultimately, this study provides scholars, policymakers, and communication practitioners with new insights into how digital PR can enhance public service delivery, strengthen democratic communication, and improve institutional credibility in developing countries.

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Recommendations

In view of the findings from the work, the following recommendations have been made.

1) The Federal Ministry of Information and National Orientation, along with public institutions, should adopt a strategic framework for integrating digital public relations into policy communication to ensure consistent and interactive citizen engagement.

2) The National Information Technology Development Agency (NITDA) and public sector agencies should invest in digital infrastructure, staff training, and simplified communication procedures to overcome barriers to effective digital public relations.

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3) Government ministries, departments, and agencies should prioritize two-way digital communication by responding promptly to public feedback on digital platforms to build public trust and enhance stakeholder participation.

4) The Federal Government, in collaboration with communication regulatory bodies and academic institutions, should implement capacity-building programs and establish a clear national digital communication policy to strengthen digital public relations practice in Nigeria.

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